

A 94-GHz SLA-enabled bandpass filter for monopulse radar in space debris detection

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Small pieces (in the range of several centimeters) of space debris are difficult to detect and potentially harmful for the satellites orbiting the Earth. Monopulse radars with high-gain antennas can be used at the millimeter-wave range where the antenna becomes more compact [1]. The antenna can improve its frequency selectivity and out-of-band behavior if it is cascaded to a narrow-band filter avoiding the radiation at undesired frequencies. However, narrow-band filters at the millimeter-wave range exhibit intricate physical features that are not easy to manufacture using conventional CNC (Computer Numerical Control) milling techniques in aluminum, for instance. In this presentation, we will explore the options given by a stereolithography (SLA) 3D-printing method combined with groove gap waveguide (GGW) technology and the use of less-sensitive higher-order modes. GGW has been previously shown to have less demands in terms of mechanical accuracy and contributes to a robust performance at millimeter-waves at above. Several realizations of the same silver-coated filter will show a promising behavior of this approach for 3D-printed filters at very high frequencies and excellent measured performance (Fig. 1). This work has been funded by the Spanish *Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación – Agencia Estatal de Investigación* (MCIN/AEI/ 10.13039/501100011033) under Projects PID2020-112545RB-C51 and PID2020-112545RB-C53.

Figure 1. a) Exploded view of the GGW filter showing the pin-bed, top-plate and transitions to the I/O ports placed at the back-plate. b) Frequency performance of some of the realizations of the same filter (a photograph of one of the prototypes is shown in the inset).

References

- [1] A. Tamayo-Domínguez, J. -M. Fernández-González, and M. Sierra-Castañer, "Monopulse Radial Line Slot Array Antenna Fed by a 3-D-Printed Cavity-Ended Modified Butler Matrix Based on Gap Waveguide at 94 GHz," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, **69**, 8, August, 2021, pp. 4558-4568, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2021.3060045.